

Joachim Griesbaum, Thomas Mandl,
Christa Womser-Hacker (Hrsg.)

Information und Wissen: global, sozial und frei?

Proceedings des 12. Internationalen Symposiums
für Informationswissenschaft (ISI 2011)

Hildesheim, 9.–11. März 2011

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Verlag Werner Hülsbusch
Fachverlag für Medientechnik und -wirtschaft

A survey of internet searching skills among intermediate school students: How librarians can help

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Abstract

The advent and development of the Internet has changed students' pattern of information seeking behaviors. That is also the case in Iran. The current research was carried out by interviewing with and observing of 20 intermediate girl students to assess their information seeking behavior on the web environment through a qualitative approach. Findings indicate an acceptable level of access to the Internet and vast use of web search engines by the girl students in Tehran. However, students' knowledge of the concept and how search engines work and also about the methods and tools of retrieving information from electronic sources other than the search engines is poor. The study also shows that, compared to the Internet, the role of libraries and librarians are gradually diminishing in fulfilling the students' information needs. Authors recommend that school librarians can provide different instructional and information literacy programs to help students improve their information seeking behavior and their knowledge of the Internet.

Keywords

Information seeking behavior, Intermediate school students, Internet, School libraries, School librarians.

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology has dynamically affected the information seeking behavior of the user. As the most effective tool in information seeking behavior, the Internet is gaining popularity among people as well as children and young adults throughout the world (Barik, Bisen & Bhardwaj, 2007). Use of the Web has proliferated in schools and all types of libraries, but little is known specially in developing countries about how young people find information on the Web (Bilal & Kirby, 2002).

Besides information resources like the family, friends and other communicational media, Web has become the main resource of information to attract students due to some advantages like easy and quick access and diversity of the contents. Nevertheless, there is not yet a comprehensive knowledge regarding students' tendencies towards the Internet and how they would use it. Also, it is not clear to what extent and in what ways they are taking advantage of this modern media. Further, the role of librarians and school libraries is also undefined. Despite many studies and researches carried out in this respect in Iran, the thesis by Alipour (2006) is the only significant work on the high school students' information seeking behavior. There still remain some big research gaps in this area.

Literature review

The widespread use of the Internet as a communication media and co-didactic tool in schools and education centers has evolved students' information seeking behavior. This has become a popular research area for scientists in the world (Madden, Ford & Miller, 2007; Madden et al, 2006; Bowler, Large & Rejskind, 2001; Large, Beheshti & Moukdad, 1999; Fidel et al, 1999; Bilal 1998, 2000, 2001, 2002) as well as in Iran (Mansourian, 2008a,

2008b; Mokhtarpour, 2007; Yaminfirouz & Davarpanah, 2004; Hayati & Tasviri Ghamsari, 2000).

In a pilot study, Bilal (1998) investigated the searching behavior and success of 22 seventh grade science students in using the Yahoo!igans!¹. Students failed in their quest mainly due to their lack of knowledge of how to use the engine. Assessment of web-based information search skills among students of elementary schools was the subject of research by Large, Beheshti and Moukdad (1999). The results showed that although the newcomers tended towards sophisticated searching strategies, in case of trouble they did not refer to the always-present search help, i.e., the librarian. A similar research was carried out at the same time by Fiedel et al. (1999) on high school students which concluded that high school students were not able to begin a search task without the help of librarians. Bilal (2001, 2002) shows that children's information seeking is influenced by their cognitive, physical and affective perspectives.

Research shows that children are more persistent and motivated in seeking information over the Web than in using traditional and online sources (Bilal, 2000). Factors such as individual differences, age, information retrieval systems used, users' cognitive and learning style, and users' online search experience are the important factor in information seeking behavior on the Web (Kim, 2001; Bilal & Kirby, 2002). In another study, Madden et al. (2006) evaluated information searching strategies and factors influencing the search performance of students aged 11 to 16 using the "thinking aloud" (expression of perceptions) approach. The search results indicated the high level of access to computer and Internet and students' relatively high knowledge of search tools and search engines. Madden, Ford and Miller (2007) focused on the information resources of students in Britain's guidance schools. They realized that students would consider the Internet as their most useful information resource

The only research on the information seeking behavior of students on the Internet environment in Iran is Alipour's thesis in 2006. He worked on the search behaviors and information seeking patterns in Tehran high schools using the behavioral patterns based on observation and Internet-oriented search. He concluded that the students' behavior in the web environment did not follow any regular pattern. Also his study showed that the Internet is the main search tool for many students to access news, educational and academic updates.

1 Yahoo!igans! is a search engine and directory designed for children ages 7 to 12.

By reviewing the related literature, one concludes that the widespread presence of the Internet has led to students' high levels of access to the Web and information resources. Their performance, however, in optimal and efficient use of different information resources of this hectic virtual world depends on their level of education and cognitive capacity. These studies also indicate that high school students encounter difficulty, including applying correct search syntax and finding relevant results and they lack relevant knowledge of how to use the internet especially the search engines.

Research design

The main aim of the present study is to assess the intermediate school students' information seeking behavior on the Internet. Based on the above aim, the research questions are as follows:

- What is the level of Internet access among intermediate school students?
- How much these student get to use the web search engines?
- What are the students' usual patterns of information searching and retrieval on the Internet?
- To what extent can they manage to consider necessary practices to get the desired results without the help of others?
- Who are the students' coaches and guides at the time of web search?
- Which one do the students prefer to use to get information: the library or the Internet?

The approach taken in this study is a mixed method approach. The researchers have taken a sample of 20 intermediate girls students from one of central Tehran's schools in three different grades based on the "available sample" method. Based on the authors' observations, a local network comprising 20 sets of computers all connected to the Internet was available in this school. In addition, to their routine schedule of source studies, the students also took part in computer skills classes like MS Word and PowerPoint. The school also had a library which, as they told the authors, had a librarian in charge.

The research instrument was the investigation inventory. The information was gathered in two stages. First, the authors collected their required data from the participants according to the investigation inventory and then interviewed the participants and observed their behavior of searching the Internet.

In order to verify the results, the investigation inventory was submitted to two specialists on information seeking behavior and their opinions and advices were adopted to modify and optimize the results.

Results

Q1. What is the level of school students' access to the Internet?

To answer this question we should first determine how long the students have been familiar to the Internet, how many hours they spend weekly on the Internet, where do they most access it, and which website they visit right after the connection is established. Table 1 shows the answers for these questions respectively.

Table 1. Intermediate school students' familiarity with and use of the Internet

Familiarity time span of students with the Internet	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 1 year	3	15%
Between 1 and 2 years	1	5%
Between 2 and 3 years	4	20%
More than 3 years	12	60%
Students' use of the Internet during the last week	Frequency	Percentage
Once	4	20%
Twice	2	10%
Three times	3	15%
Four times and more	10	50%
No use	1	5%
Access location to the Internet	Frequency	Percentage
School	0	0%
Home	20	100%
Coffee net	0	0%
Library	0	0%
The first section students visit right after the connection is established	Frequency	Percentage
Electronic mail	2	10%
Chat	2	10%
Search engines	14	70%
Weblogs	0	0
News websites	0	0
Discussion forums	0	0
Web-sites of interest	2	10%

As can be seen, the students' knowledge of the Internet and their use of it are at relatively good levels. They access the Internet from home more frequently than from their school. As is demonstrated in table 1, the search engines are the main places where the students visit right after accessing the Internet. This reveals the high priority these search engines have as sources of information for the students. It is worth noting that most of the students spoke of "Google" instead of phrases like "search engines". This highlights the significant role of "Google" as the predominant search tool for intermediate school students.

Regarding the students' search skills, two questions were posed: the first concerned their self-assessment regarding skills in using the Internet. The second, in verification of the first one, assessed their levels of success in accessing their required information in their last search attempt. The answers to these two queries are listed in tables 2.

Table 2. Students' self-assessment of their Internet skills

Internet skills	Frequency	Percentage
High	8	40%
Moderate	10	50%
Low	2	2%
Success in finding needed info in the last Internet session	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	16	80%
No	4	20%

As is evident in table 2, most students assessed their Internet skills as average or high, and that is confirmed by their success in their last attempts. Only 4 out of 20 students (that would be 20%) did not get what they wanted from the web searches and believed that their failure was due to reasons such as lack of skills, relatively low speed of the Internet and poor knowledge of English language (in case of search in English).

Q2. To what extent students use the web search engines?

This question was posed because of the great appeal these search engines had for intermediate school students (table 1). Therefore, first their level of knowledge about search engines was evaluated. Then the frequency of their use of different search engines and the mostly used ones were determined. Tables 3 to 6 demonstrate the results.

Table 3. Intermediate students' knowledge of search engine

Students' knowledge of search engine	Frequency	Percentage
Students who knew	11	55%
Students who did not know	9	45%

Although search engines are the most popular Internet tools among the students, most of them were unable to come up with a clear definition of these tools. Usually they are not familiar with expressions like “search engines” and would rather know about some particular tools like “Google” and “Yahoo” which is not a surprising fact. The definitions given by the students for “Search engines” are as follows:

- “Search engines are things giving us the information we need”
- “A web-site which retrieves some data as we enter our words there”
- “A web-site which retrieves some data as we enter our words and click”
- “A search engines will search for what we have asked for”
- “We get our needed info from search engines”
- “Those web-sites where one could find whatever they are looking for”
- “Search engines are tools to find our requested web-sites”

The definitions given by the students imply their relative knowledge of the functions and performances of search engines. No one knew about search engine concepts and structure and its working mechanism and only spoke of their applications and tasks.

Table 4. Use of the search engines by the students

Using the search engines	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	20	100%
No	0	0%
Extent of use	Frequency	Percentage
High	15	75%
Average	5	25%
Little	0	0%

The data in table 4 verify those of table 1 and indicate the significance of search engines for the students.

Table 5. The frequency of students' use of each search engine

search engines	Frequency	Percentage
Google	20	100%
Yahoo	19	95%
Microsoft	1	5%
Altavista	0	0%
Yahoo kids search engine	0	0%

Table 5 shows the most popular search engines from the students' points of view. According to their own remarks, students use Google more than Yahoo because they believe Google returns more and pertinent results.

Table 6. The extent of students' knowledge about search engines and their use

	Frequency	Percentage
Those who knew	3	15%
Those who did not know	17	85%

Although the use of search engines makes access to information on the Internet much easier and more efficient and reduces the retrieval of irrelevant information, none of the students had knowledge about these tools. The data in table 6 shows that the only 15% of the students who had heard the search engine names, did not use them and had not any idea how to use them. It is obvious that when they do not have a clear definition of the search engines, they would not know anything about the search operators.

Q3. What are the students' patterns for searching and retrieving information on the Internet?

Pattern here means the approach students take in using the search engines. For this purpose, first the average amount of time spent weekly by each student in searching the Internet is taken into consideration. Then their aim and approach to get those required information from the Internet was questioned. The answers to these queries are listed in tables 7 and 8.

According to above tables, half of the students were spending only two hours per week in search of information on the Internet and considered this amount of time to be adequate. 85% of them pursued the aim of finding some school-texts to do assignments (for research purposes). Furthermore, 55% were looking to download movies and music clips by searching the web (for entertainment).

Table 7. Pattern of the search engine use by the students

Average amount of time spent weekly on the Internet	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 2 hours	10	50%
2 hours	1	5%
Between 2 and 4 hours	5	25%
More than 4 hours	4	4%
Purpose of searching the Internet	Frequency	Percentage
Schoolwork resource identification to do school work	17	85%
Interest in gathering research info	7	35%
Downloading music and movies	11	55%
Listening to music and radio	5	25%
News	3	15%
Games	5	25%
Surfing the web	2	10%
No particular purpose	0	0%
Other purposes	4	20%

Table 8. Approach used by the students to find information on the web

Approach to find their needed information	Frequency	Percentage
Use of search engines	20	100%
Trial and error	2	10%
Searching online encyclopedia	10	50%
Searching online databases and web-sites	5	25%
Searching electronic resources	2	10%
Other approaches	1	5%

All the students used search engines to find their needed information. This supports the data in tables 1 and 4. The online encyclopedias were the second frequently used sources of information. Half the students were using sources such as Wikipedia as a definite example of electronic encyclopedias.

Q4. To what extent can intermediate school students follow related practices to find information on the web without getting help from others?

For this stage of the research, in which interviews were carried out along with observation, the students were asked to search for a specific topic on the web. It was obvious from the beginning that students were not able to find suitable keywords to initiate and formulate their search (a verification of what Fiedel et al. had found out). So the appropriate search keywords were

given to them or they were asked to simply repeat their last successful web search. All the students were using Google. The authors observed that some of the students could not enter the Google in the address bar without help. As for the website address, they were requested to explain each section of the address but none of them could come up with any explanation due to lack of knowledge.

Table 9. Search practices followed by the students

Practices followed by the students	Frequency	Percentage
Distinguishing the most relevant resources	12	60%
Navigating the websites	8	40%
Choice of useful pages and sites	50	50%
Using site-maps	0	0
Saving information	12	60%
Defining addresses	0	0

The data in table 9 indicate that most of students (60%) managed to pick up relevant resources through the search engines. They knew how to select the relevant resources. Their navigation skills were weak and they did not know about the site maps and their use. As for saving of information, 60% of the students could store their obtained information. It was interesting that some students copied the webpages and pasted them into the MS Word environment as a way to save their found data.

Q5.

Who are the students' coaches and guides in surfing and searching the web?

Here, coaches and guides are those who have taught the students how to surf the web and get their information.

In this stage two questions were posed to the participants: first, who initially taught them how to use the Internet? And secondly, to whom do the students refer as they encounter a problem? Tables 10 and 12 contain the answers to these questions.

Table 10.

First teachers of the students on the Internet and web search strategies

First teachers of students on Internet	Frequency	Percentage
School librarians	0	0
Family and relatives	17	85%
Class mates	2	10%
Teachers	0	0
Experienced people	0	0
Participating in instructional courses	0	0
Study of guide books	0	0
Using Trial and error approach	1	5%

Table 11. *Intermediate school students' guides at the time of web surfing*

Students' guides at the time of web surfing troubles	Frequency	Percentage
School librarians	0	0
Family	16	80%
Classmates	1	5%
Teachers	0	0
Experienced people	1	5%
Others	2	10%

It is observed from comparing tables 10 and 11 that the majority (80%) of students has initially learned to surf the web at home. Hence, their families have had a significant role in their getting to know the Internet. As they have learned to explore the web at home and because of their adequate access to the Internet (see table 1), they go to a member of their families to get help in searching the web. The interesting fact regarding the last two tables is the absence of teachers and librarians as students' guides at the time web-search. A reason for this may be the fact that many schools do not have Internet access for students and the teachers are not familiar with the Web.

In order to determine how much the school library and the librarian have been effective in satisfying the students' information needs, first the students' average weekly reference to the library, and their purpose of going to the library should be determined. It should be determined whether they have found their required information in the library and what the role of the librarian has been in this regard. Table 12 will answer these questions.

Table 12. Students' weekly use and purpose of using the school library

Students' weekly use	Frequency	Percentage
Once	9	45%
Twice	4	20%
Three times	0	0
4 times or more	2	10%
Never go to the library	5	25%
Purposes of going to the library	Frequency	Percentage
Doing school works	6	30%
Non-school studies	12	60%
Enhance their knowledge	8	40%
Interest in gathering scientific data	9	45%
Finding information to do extra-curricular activities	4	20%

Although it is stated that libraries play an important role in educational and cultural progresses of students, in practice they do not have any high position in the students' using of the Internet. It is so unfortunate that 5 out of 20 guidance school students (25%) have never gone to the school library.

Findings in table 12 indicate that the students often (60%) use the library for extra-curricula studies and get information to upgrade their knowledge. These results are in agreement with the finding in the first part of the same table which shows that encyclopedias are the most frequently used resources of information at these places. Because of their wide coverage of different subjects and high quality, encyclopedias could serve as useful resources to satisfy students' information needs and their scientific curiosities.

Q6. Which one do the students prefer to use to get information: the library or the Internet?

The findings here are not only unexpected but they also confirm the results of previous questions regarding the minor role of school libraries and librarians in helping students in their information seeking process. As is evident in table 13, unlike the minor role of school libraries, the Internet plays a significant role in fulfilling students' information thirst. The majority of students participating in the research (95%) believed the easy ways to access information on the Internet and its adequacy and availability make the Internet their number one priority over the library.

Table 13. The contribution of Internet and library in meeting students' informational needs.

	Frequency	Percentage
Internet	19	95%
Library	1	5%

Conclusions

Although the research population was small we can have some general conclusions regarding the information seeking behavior of Iranian intermediate school students on the Web: Many Iranian intermediate school students access the Internet from home rather than their schools. The reason for not using the Internet at school seems to be the lack of access or lack of enough free time.

Due to their ease of use, and facilities for seeking information on the Web, search engines have a high popularity among school students. Google and Yahoo lead the leading way. However, due to the lack of thorough instruction, their knowledge of these tools is limited to and they have no conceptual or structural understanding about them. Similar to the findings of other studies (for example by Madden et al, 2006; Dersang, 2005; Bilal, 1998, 2000, 2001, 2002; Bilal & Kirby, 2002; Large, Beheshti & Moukdad, 1999) school students have cognitive difficulties in formulating effective search queries, applying correct search syntax, term relationships, and subject hierarchies. In case there is no organized information literacy instruction at schools and in the absence of librarians as trainers of the new generation, the family bears the heavy task of guiding the students in searching the Internet. This may be the result of the students' lack of access to the Internet at school and at the school library that has led to the insignificant role of librarians in this regard. Although the students have gained knowledge through their families on how to acquire their needed information on the web, a lack of instruction to help students in conducting their searches is readily felt. The advent and development of the Internet has evolved the information seeking behavior. In this changing scenario, library and information centers have to focus towards the user community to understand their changing information needs and information seeking behaviors (Barik, Bisen & Bhardwaj, 2007). Also

despite the libraries' significant role in elevating students' knowledge, they have not yet taken their right position in schools. This could be due to the weakness of school libraries in providing information literacy workshops to students, and lack of providing access to the Internet, and most importantly, lack of integration between courses and the library resources including access to information resources on the Web.

Based on the results of this research, the following recommendations can be made to overcome the existing shortcomings: Providing information literacy courses by the school library will encourage students to use the library as a learning environment (like a class) and the librarians as a teacher. School can also offer curriculum-related user instruction that include use of the Web. This instruction cover basic search strategies in using selected search engines (Bilal & Kirby, 2002).

Use of the Web in intermediate schools and the increased access to the Web by students at home & school raise many issues concerning information-seeking and use. Here the role of school librarians and teachers in educating and training students becomes more important. School IT sites could be located in school libraries in order to give the librarians an important role in improving information seeking behaviors of students.

School teachers can play an important role in encouraging students to use the library and a learning media center. Thus the use of the Internet and online resources can be managed through the integration of the teacher-librarian cooperation into the curricula with the benefits of instructing the students how to use the Internet and how to evaluate information sources on the Web from the curricular point of view.

Establishing and developing better school libraries with access to the Internet will help students not to rely on people other than librarians and teachers in learning how to search and use information sources whether printed or electronic.

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